
Digital Technological Knowledge and Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between digital technological knowledge and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two (2) research questions were posed while two (2) corresponding hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was 264 Business Education postgraduate (2023/2024 academic session) duly registered Masters (M.Ed/M.Sc and Ph.D) students from public universities (both Federal and State) in South-South, Nigeria. The instruments for data collection were two sets of structured questionnaire titled; Digital Technological Knowledge Questionnaire (DTKQ) and Entrepreneurship Intentions Questionnaire (EIQ) which were developed by the researchers. The instruments validated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to answer research questions and testing of hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study show that innovative capabilities and problem-solving skills have positive relationship with development of entrepreneurship intentions. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that universities in South-South, Nigeria should embed dedicated courses or modules on problem solving strategies in digital technologies in their Business Education programmes. Students should be exposed to activities such as stimulation, real-life case studies that can demand creativity and informed decision making, group problem-solving exercises that can help their ability to effectively identify and address entrepreneurial challenges and devise solutions.

Keywords: Digital Technological Knowledge, Entrepreneurship Intentions, Business Education, Innovative Capabilities, Problem-Solving

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship intention refers to an individual's psychological state and commitment to starting a new business. It encompasses the motivation, planning, and readiness to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The concept is shaped by various factors such as personal attitudes, perceived feasibility and desirability of the entrepreneurial endeavour, social norms, and perceived behavioural control. Essentially, it reflects the degree to which an individual is determined and prepared to embark on an entrepreneurship journey. That is to say, this intention indicates potentiality, attitude and desirable plans of an entrepreneur to start business in the future.

Similarly, Nicole (2018) defines entrepreneurship intentions as "a conscious state of mind that directs attention, experience, and action toward a specific goal or pathway to start a new business." These definitions highlight the cognitive and motivational components of entrepreneurship intentions, emphasizing the role of personal attitudes, social influences, and perceived control over the entrepreneurship process. The theory-based perspectives provided by Ikpesu (2023) and Nicole (2018) suggest that entrepreneurship intentions are shaped by both internal factors, such as individual mindset, motivation, and external factors, such as societal norms and perceived feasibility. Building on these established definitions, a new definition of entrepreneurship intentions can be formulated. Thus, entrepreneurship intentions is the deliberate and purposeful inclination to engage in entrepreneurial activities, driven by an individual's cognitive assessment of their abilities, the perceived support or barriers from their social environment, and the envisioned outcomes of entrepreneurship.

The development of entrepreneurship intentions is critical to fostering innovation, economic growth, and job creation within the society. The cultivation of entrepreneurship intentions also plays a significant role in addressing unemployment, particularly among young people, by equipping them with the mindset and skills necessary to pursue self-employment and entrepreneurial ventures. By understanding and nurturing these intentions, policymakers, educators, and business leaders can better support potential entrepreneurs, leading to the creation of new businesses that drive economic dynamism and competitiveness. Furthermore, in today's rapidly evolving digital economy, the development of entrepreneurship intentions is increasingly intertwined with the acquisition and application of digital technological knowledge. As technology continues to advance, the ability to leverage digital resources has become a critical factor in the success of entrepreneurship endeavours.

Moreover, digital tools and platforms have become essential for fostering entrepreneurial behaviours and skills among students. These digital tools can enhance the utilization of online platforms for e-learning and e-marketing which is vital for the development of entrepreneurship intentions. As such, the personal motivation, commitment, positive attitude, entrepreneurial skills and digital technological knowledge have a significant impact on shaping the entrepreneurship intention. Firstly, possessing a strong foundation in digital technology equips individuals with the skills needed to identify and leverage online tools, resources and platforms essential for launching and managing modern businesses. This knowledge enhances their ability to recognize digital market opportunities, streamline operations and effectively reach target audiences in competitive digital environments. Thus, digital technological knowledge refers to the understanding and application of digital tools, platforms, and systems that are essential for navigating the modern business landscape.

Akpomi and Nwiyor (2023) conducted a study to investigate the factors affecting the innovative potential of postgraduate entrepreneurship in the Business Education department at Rivers State University. The research, focused on the 2021/2022 academic session, involved 73 participants, comprising 30 instructors and 43 postgraduate students. Using a descriptive survey design, the study posed three research questions and employed the entire population due to its manageable size. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, developed based on existing literature and validated by three experts, two from Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all from the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The instrument's reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.82. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

The study revealed that instructional facilities such as textbooks, business model canvases, and ICT resources were insufficient to foster innovative potential in postgraduate entrepreneurship. Consequently, it recommended the provision of resources like mentorship programs, incubators, and industry connections to enhance the educational experience. This study aligns with the present research in emphasizing the importance of entrepreneurship and fostering entrepreneurial mindsets among postgraduate students. However, while Akpomi and Nwiyor focused on factors influencing innovative potential, the present study investigates the relationship between innovative capabilities and the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Onwubuya and Ikechukwu (2023) conducted a study on innovative capabilities and entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education students in tertiary institutions. The research examined how advancements in technology are revolutionizing the operations of the 21st-century business environment. The study adopted a survey design, with a population comprising 338 third-year Business Education students from four public tertiary institutions offering Business Education programs in Anambra State during the 2022/2023 academic session. Data were collected using two structured questionnaires and analyzed using the Bivariate Pearson Correlation matrix and simple linear regression techniques. The results revealed that innovative capabilities such as technology skills, digital communication, digital safety, and social media literacy were significantly associated with the entrepreneurship intentions of Business Education students. The similarity between this study and the current research lies in their shared emphasis on the importance of technology skills, digital communication, and social media literacy as critical components for business success in an era defined by emerging technologies.

Similarly, Ching (2024) conducted a study on the effect of innovative capabilities on social entrepreneurship intentions and nascent behaviours among students and practitioners in mass communication. The study adopted a quantitative survey method, with 814 participants (373 students and 441 practitioners) providing valid responses. Data were analyzed using structural equation modeling. The results indicated positive direct effects of perceived social support, perceived social awareness of peers, and innovative capabilities on social entrepreneurship intentions, as well as positive direct effects of innovative capabilities and social entrepreneurship intentions on social entrepreneurial behaviours. The study identified innovative capabilities as a critical factor for fostering social entrepreneurship intentions and behaviours. The similarity with the present study lies in their shared emphasis on innovative capabilities as a pivotal element for promoting entrepreneurship intentions.

In a related study, Made and Nyoman (2023) examined innovative potential, privacy violation experiences, and their impact on online purchase intentions. The purpose of the

research was to explain the effects of innovative potential and consumer privacy violation experiences on the online purchase intentions of millennial consumer groups in Denpasar City and Badung Regency, Bali. The study population consisted of millennial consumers in these regions who had engaged in online shopping. Using a purposive sampling method, the study sampled 200 respondents. Data analysis involved descriptive statistical analysis and moderated regression analysis (MRA). The results indicated that innovative potential had a positive and significant effect on online repurchase intention, while privacy violation experiences had a negative and significant effect on repurchase intentions.

Furthermore, privacy violation experiences moderated (weakened) the effect of innovative potential on online repurchases intentions among millennial consumer groups in Denpasar City and Badung Regency. This study relates to the present research in that both emphasize the role and importance of innovative potential in shaping intentions. While Made and Nyoman highlighted the positive significance of innovative potential in online purchase behaviour, the present study focuses on its importance in fostering entrepreneurship intentions. Sepulveda and Collazos (2023) conducted a study on innovation capabilities, innovation strategies and performance: an empirical analysis in SMEs. The study investigates the impact on the economies of developing countries.

This study explores the relationship between innovation capabilities, innovation strategy and financial performance in a sample of 136 SMEs from Valle del Cauca– Colombia. The study used a structural equation model to analyse how this relationship could inform the management of innovation in SMEs. This study demonstrated positive relationships between innovation capabilities and innovation strategy, as well as between these two variables and financial performance. The results indicate that not all strategies generate good performance and although cooperation is one of the best performing strategies. The results of the analysis of the measurement model that relates innovation capabilities with the innovation strategy and financial performance (hypotheses H1, H2 and H3) are confirmed.

It is evident that, according to the innovation capabilities, SMEs determine the innovation strategy to use. However, not all strategies impact financial performance in the same way. Study suggests that Cooperation strategies should be used more by SMEs since it allows them to make up for the lack of internal capabilities that they require to innovate. Thus, the relationship this study and the present study they both discuss the impact of innovative capabilities on performance and outcomes. However, the topics are not completely the same, the study of Sapulveda and Collazos emphasized on innovation capabilities and strategies, both studies are on innovative capabilities for entrepreneurship.

Adiele, Ubah, and Onyeiwu (2024) and Akpomi, Kayii and Nwile (2022) studies examined innovative entrepreneurial skills and their implications for sustainable development in Nigeria. A survey design was used, targeting undergraduate students across Nigerian universities. A sample of 300 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire, analyzed using regression analysis. The study found that innovative skills like critical thinking and creativity significantly enhance entrepreneurship intentions.

Similarly, Iweh, Yukongdi and Bhujel (2021), assessed the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education programs in Nigerian public universities. Using a mixed-method approach, data were gathered from 250 students selected via purposive sampling. Instruments included surveys and interviews, with thematic analysis and regression techniques. Findings revealed that entrepreneurship education improved problem-solving and innovation capabilities,

thereby fostering entrepreneurship intentions. In the work of Dada, Adegbuyi, and Ogbari, (2023), who examined the effect of entrepreneurial attributes on venture creation among undergraduates in South West Nigeria. A total of 616 students from public and private universities participated, selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected via questionnaires and analyzed using structural equation modeling. The study concluded that creativity, leadership, and critical thinking strongly predicted entrepreneurship intentions.

In another related work, Ewumi, Okeke, and Adeoye (2012) investigated Entrepreneurship Education as a solution to youth unemployment, this study adopted a survey design focusing on university students in Lagos, Nigeria. Using simple random sampling, 105 students participated. The study employed regression analysis to establish that Entrepreneurship Education enhanced innovative skills and entrepreneurial aspirations. Gafar, Jones and Sharma (2014) and Ikpesu and Kayii (2023) evaluated the impact of experiential learning on entrepreneurial skill development among Nigerian students. A sample of 400 students was drawn using quota sampling. Questionnaires were analyzed through ANOVA, which demonstrated that experiential learning positively influenced both problem-solving skills and entrepreneurship intentions.

The study of Gyamfi (2014) assessed entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions among Ghanaian students exposed to Entrepreneurship Education. Using stratified sampling, 194 students were surveyed with validated instruments. Data analysis with linear regression showed a direct link between innovative capability training and the students' entrepreneurial drive.

Rocha, Moraes and Fischer (2021) conducted a study to evaluate the micro foundations of students entrepreneurship, a cornerstone of innovation ecosystems. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the micro foundations of student entrepreneurship, a cornerstone of innovation ecosystems. A quantitative approach based on multivariate data analysis using confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling was applied to a sample of 420 respondents. Findings highlighted the importance of Entrepreneurship Education in nurturing problem-solving skills, which translated to entrepreneurship intentions. Findings indicate that the university environment positively influences entrepreneurial behavior and intention in students. Nonetheless, further integration between academia and external dimensions of the ecosystems is necessary to drive more intense entrepreneurial intentions. This finding suggests a relative lack of propensity of students from São Paulo to engage in entrepreneurial venturing. Results highlight the necessary conditions for universities to foster entrepreneurial activity and, incidentally, feed innovation ecosystems with entrepreneurial talent.

Olawoyin and Adegoke (2018) conducted a study on Business Education Students' creative abilities needed for self-reliance in Oyo State College of Education, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 749, with a sample of 261 respondents drawn from the three Colleges of Education in Oyo State. A structured questionnaire containing 36 items was used to elicit responses and generate data for the study. The instrument, face-validated by three experts from the Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Kuder-Richardson formula (K-R4), yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.81. The data were analyzed using mean to address the research questions and standard deviation to assess the consistency of responses, while t-test statistics were used to test the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that Business Education students needed skills and capabilities in problem-solving within accounting, marketing, and information and

communication technology. Additionally, the findings indicated that students required creative abilities for innovativeness to achieve self-reliance.

While both studies are similar in addressing the problem-solving skills needed by Business Education students and their relevance for successful business operations and self-reliance, they differ in focus. Olawoyin and Adegoke's study examines Business Education students' creative abilities needed for self-reliance in Oyo State College of Education, Nigeria, whereas the present study investigates the relationship between innovative capabilities and the development of entrepreneurship intentions. In a related research, Kingsley (2019) conducted a research titled; the determinants of career choice among Business Education students in Rivers State. Six research question and six null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 605, which consisted of all level one hundred Business Education students in Rivers State University. A sample size of 250 was randomly selected from the study population through the random sampling technique. The instrument was validated by a measurement and evaluation expert and two Business Educators from faculty of Technical and Science Education, Rivers State. The Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (PPMC) was used to measure the reliability of the instrument. The data collected were analyzed using mean ratings and standard deviation from the research questions and Z-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance.

The study revealed that interest influence the choice of career in Business Education at high Extent. The findings further revealed that business skills, career prospects influenced the choice of career in Business Education while parents and peer groups have significant influence on the choice of the career in Business Education. Skills, ability and career prospects: Departments of Business Education in Universities should also ensure that career programmes, talks, seminars are organized periodically for students to prepare them to understand needs of their career. This is to equip students with necessary skills to successfully engage in innovations and to solve problems in business creations. This study is related to the present study in that they both address perception of students towards Entrepreneurship. The studies are different in that the present study focused on non-business students, while the other study focused on Business Education Students.

However, despite the recognized potential of entrepreneurship to address these challenges, there remains a critical gap in understanding the factors that influence or contributes to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among this demographic. One of the pivotal factors in contemporary entrepreneurship is digital technological knowledge. Studies have shown that digital technological knowledge enhances entrepreneurship intentions by providing students with the skills necessary to recognize opportunities, develop innovative complex market environments. Yet, there is limited empirical research exploring how digital technological knowledge specifically develops the entrepreneurship intentions of postgraduate students in South-South universities. Given the crucial role of digital skills in modern entrepreneurship, it is imperative to investigate whether postgraduate students in this region possess the necessary digital technological knowledge and how this knowledge influences their entrepreneurial aspirations. Moreover, understanding the barriers to acquiring and applying digital technologies in entrepreneurial endeavours is essential for the development of entrepreneurship intentions.

This study, therefore, seeks to address the following problem: What is the relationship between innovative capabilities, what is the relationship between problem-solving skills and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigerias? Furthermore, what are the key digital technologies

that impact these intentions, and what challenges do students face in leveraging digital tools for entrepreneurship? Addressing these questions is vital for crafting effective strategies to enhance entrepreneurship programmes in this Geo-political zone which will develop student's entrepreneurship intentions ultimately contributing to economic development and job creation.

Purpose of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the relationship between digital technological knowledge and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education Postgraduate Students in universities in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine:

1. The relationship between innovative capabilities and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.
2. The relationship between problem-solving skills and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does innovative capabilities relate to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria?
2. How does problem-solving skills relate to development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between innovative capabilities and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria?
2. There is no significant relationship between problem-solving skills and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. Dayon (2019) defined correlational research design as one, where the researcher establishes a relationship between two or more variables. This design is appropriate for the study since it intends to establish a relationship between digital technological knowledge and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

The population of this study consisted of two hundred and sixty four (264) duly registered Business Education postgraduate students (2023/2024 Year 1) in the ten (10) public universities offering Business Education programme at postgraduate level in South-South Geo-political zone of Nigeria. Due to the small nature of the population, the researcher decided to use the entire population of two hundred and sixty four (264) Business Education postgraduate M.Ed/ M.Sc students (2023/2024) since the population of this study is comfortable. The research instruments used for the study were validated structured questionnaires made up of two parts containing twelve (12) items on "Digital Technological

Knowledge Questionnaire (DTKQ)” and ten (10) items on “Entrepreneurship Intentions Questionnaire (EIQ)” respectively. The reliability of the instruments were determined using test re-test method and data were analysed with PPMC to obtain the coefficients of 0.90 and 0.89 respectively. Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). While the null hypothesis was also tested at 0.05 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) with social science (SPSS 23).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: How does innovative capabilities relate to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on how innovative capabilities relate to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities South-South, Nigeria

		innovative capabilities	Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Level of Correlation
innovative capabilities	Pearson Correlation	1	.788**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	264	264	
Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Pearson Correlation	.788**	1	strong positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	264	264	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' SPSS Statistical Output (2025).

Table 1 presents the result of the relationship between innovative capabilities and the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.788 indicates a strong and positive relationship between the two variables (innovative capabilities and the development of entrepreneurship intentions).

Research Question 2: How does problem-solving skills relate to development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in South-South universities?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on how problem-solving skills relate to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities South-South, Nigeria

		problem-solving skills	Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Level of Correlation
problem-solving skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.756**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	264	264	Strong Positive Relationship
Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Pearson Correlation	.756**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	264	264	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' SPSS Statistical Output (2025).

Table 2 presents the result of the relationship between problem-solving skills and the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.756 indicates a strong and positive relationship between the two variables (problem-solving skills and the development of entrepreneurship intentions). The strong positive correlation indicates that post graduate students with higher problem-solving skills are more likely to exhibit strong entrepreneurship intentions. This finding suggests that problem-solving skills are a critical determinant of entrepreneurship intentions. Students who can effectively address challenges and devise solutions are more likely to engage in entrepreneurial activities, as these skills are vital for navigating the complexities of entrepreneurship.

Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between innovative capabilities and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria

Table 3: Analysis on the Significant Relationship between innovative capabilities and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

		innovative capabilities	Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Level of Correlation
innovative capabilities	Pearson Correlation	1	.788**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	264	264	Sig
Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Pearson Correlation	.788**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	264	264	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' SPSS Statistical Output (2024).

Data on Table 3 above showed the relationship is statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p=0.000$, $p=0.000$, $N= 264$). The p -value being less than the threshold of 0.01 confirms that the observed relationship is not due to random chance but represents a genuine association between innovative capabilities and entrepreneurship intentions.

H₀₂ There is no significant relationship between problem solving skills and development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria

Table 4: Analysis on the Significant Relationship between problem-solving skills relate to the development of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students in universities in South-South, Nigeria

		problem-solving skills	Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Level of Correlation
problem-solving skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.756**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	264	264	Sig
Development of Entrepreneurship Intentions	Pearson Correlation	.756**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	264	264	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Data on Table 4.above showed the relationship is statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p=0.000$, $p=0.000$, $N= 264$). The p -value being less than the threshold of 0.01 confirms that the observed relationship is not due to random chance but represents a genuine association between problem solving skills and entrepreneurship intentions.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the first research question indicate that Business Education postgraduate students strongly perceive a positive relationship between innovative capabilities and the development of entrepreneurship intentions. Respondents affirmed their ability to generate new business ideas, launch business brands, design company websites, and implement innovative processes and products. These perceptions align with previous research by Ching (2024) and Made and Nyoman (2023), who emphasized the critical role of innovative capabilities in fostering entrepreneurship intentions. Similarly, Onwubuya and Ikechukwu (2023) also highlighted the transformative impact of digital technological innovations in today's business environment. The study found that specific innovative competencies, such as digital communication, digital safety, and social media literacy, are significantly associated with entrepreneurial aspirations. This supports the argument that students' intrinsic innovative abilities and experiential learning are more instrumental in shaping their entrepreneurial intentions than external factors like material or infrastructural resources.

Conversely, the current findings contradict those of Akpomi and Nwiyor (2023) and Sepulveda and Collazos (2023), who attributed the limitations in entrepreneurial development primarily to infrastructural deficiencies rather than individual competencies. The present study emphasizes that personal innovative potential is a more decisive factor in influencing entrepreneurial intentions. These findings further echo the conclusions of Svarc and Davic

(2016), who asserted that innovation capabilities are essential for organizations seeking to navigate challenges and leverage new opportunities. Thus, the study underscores innovative capabilities as a fundamental driver of entrepreneurship intentions among postgraduate students in South-South Nigeria.

Regarding the second research question, the study revealed a strong consensus among respondents that problem-solving skills significantly contribute to the development of entrepreneurship intentions. Students reported being able to analyze complex business problems, devise practical solutions, and confidently address digital and operational challenges in entrepreneurship. These insights are consistent with the findings of Adiele et al. (2024), Dada et al. (2023), and Iweh et al. (2021), who also identified problem-solving skills as a key motivator for entrepreneurial pursuits. Furthermore, Ewumi, Okeke, and Adeoye (2021) emphasized that students equipped to handle unfamiliar business problems and troubleshoot digital challenges are more inclined to develop entrepreneurial intentions. The present findings reinforce this view, especially within the context of a rapidly evolving digital economy where entrepreneurship increasingly relies on the application of digital knowledge and adaptive problem-solving. However, Rocha et al. (2022) offered a contrasting perspective, noting that institutional support may not significantly influence the development of entrepreneurial traits. The current study suggests instead that students' abilities to independently resolve business challenges are crucial to cultivating entrepreneurial intentions.

Conclusion

This study concludes that both innovative capabilities and problem-solving skills emerge as critical internal drivers of entrepreneurship intentions among Business Education postgraduate students. The findings highlight the importance of empowering students with these competencies to navigate and thrive in the contemporary entrepreneurial landscape.

Recommendations

Based on findings of this study, the following recommendations were made, that;

1. Government and universities policies in South-South, Nigeria should prioritize funding for research and development in innovation among postgraduate students. Providing grant, scholarships, and seed funding to support students' innovative projects that can inspire confidence and enhance their entrepreneurship intentions.
2. Universities in South-South, Nigeria should embed dedicated courses or modules on problem-solving strategies in on digital technologies in their Business Education programmes. Students should be exposed to activities such as stimulation, real-life case studies that can demand creativity and informed decision making, group problem-solving exercises that can help their ability to effectively identify and address entrepreneurial challenges and devise solutions.

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